

International Migration And Brain Drain In Particular

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Abstract

The outmigration of highly educated people from a country is what's known as a "brain drain," and it's a problem in many countries. "Trade, education, and skilled human resources for trained health professionals" are the areas that are most negatively impacted by the brain drain, according to Dodani and LaPorte (2005). Brain drain may have beneficial impacts, such as creative and skilled individuals leaving their own nation to develop and discover who they are, and it can also enable immigrants to spend time living in other countries. The brain drain may also have unintended consequences, such as a reduction in human capital (Dodani and LaPorte, 2005, p. 488). Not only does relocating bright people to regions with ideal circumstances for development contribute to globalization, but it also helps contribute to the impression that the whole globe is just one big, happy family. The end effect of this is a rise not just in the average level of human capital but also in the total levels of economic productivity (Stark, 2004, p. 15). Although there are certain positive outcomes that may be attributed to brain drain, overall, it has more unfavorable consequences. This is true not just for the economy of the nation from which educated people travel, but also for the

economy of the nation to which these persons eventually go. The loss of intellectual talent is by far the most significant factor contributing to the inability of developing nations to catch up with other nations in terms of technological advancement. People opt to leave their nation for a variety of reasons, the top three being a lack of employment prospects, social injustice, and financial instability. It represents the biggest number of people who want to leave their nation in search of better professional opportunities elsewhere. According to Davis and Hart (2010), "In 2000, a person with a university or graduate degree was legally able to be six times more likely to migrate than a person with less than one education." This means that people who can contribute to the growth of the economy, and therefore the growth of the nation, are leaving the country.

Keywords: *International Migration in the World, Brain Drain, Cause of Brain Drain, Causes of Intercountry Migration, Effects of Brain Drain, Cause – Effect Relationships of Brain Drain*

1. Introduction

People with an elevated level of education and experience contribute significantly to the economy on a worldwide scale. Instead, developing nations continue to struggle with a wide variety of problems, including severe poverty, a lack of technological improvements, and a lack of chances. The capabilities of developed nations continue to improve through time, whereas the capabilities of underdeveloped countries continue to deteriorate. Because of this, industrialized nations now have an overwhelming number of competent employees attempting to enter the workforce, yet they have fewer jobs available. The United States of America continues to be the most significant hub in the global network of movement for highly trained workers (Davis and Hart, 2010, p. 511). Over the course of the previous several decades, there has been a general growth in the number of immigrants entering the United States, and it is anticipated that this trend will continue until the year 2020. The brain drain is solely responsible for a great deal of the difficulties that now exist. There is also the chance that emerging nations would incur economic losses, which will further retard their development and prevent them from producing people with a higher level of intelligence.

One of the arguments that has been made against the phenomenon that has been dubbed the "brain drain" is that the loss of knowledgeable people because of people leaving their home country will have a negative impact on the citizens of the country to which they will move. The country will not be able to compete successfully on a global scale and will become more cut off from the rest of the world if its most talented and educated citizens continue to emigrate. Without these individuals, the nation's progress would not have been possible. Isolation can cause a country's growth and progress to slow even more, which can even lead to the impoverishment of the nation. Developed nations often have a technological advantage over less developed countries, which, depending on the circumstance, might vary from a few years to a few decades.

For instance, if a person lives in a country like the United States, in which almost everyone is connected to the internet via a device that they can fit in the pocket of their pants, then that person is connected to almost everyone else living in the country. In the meantime, many developing countries are struggling with widespread power outages, which force the general population to work and play in the dark or rely on kerosene lamps for illumination. These individuals are cut off from the rest of society in areas of the economy and many aspects of life that are characterized by rapid change and rapid innovation, such as the conduct of scientific research and business transactions. In a substantial number of these locations, medical technology is likewise rather far behind where it ought to be. When residents are forced to worry more about illness and death, as well as the inability to pay for treatment or even access care, highly educated people are more likely to feel compelled to leave their country in search of a more developed country. This is because residents are forced to worry more about illness and death, as well as the inability to pay for treatment or even access care.

In their article titled "Eight Questions About Brain Drain," Professor of Economics John Gibson and Senior Economist David McKenzie emphasize that the issue of brain drain should be taken very seriously by economists not only because of its possible consequences for the economy of Turkey, but also because of its possible consequences for the economy of the overall world. This is the true not just for a nation in the process of economic and social development, but also for the global economy and social sphere. A brain drain may set off a chain reaction known as the "Domino

effect," which has the potential to have devastating consequences. Logically speaking, it is very harmful to both developed countries and developing countries to fill the developed countries with highly educated workers while at the same time consuming the developing countries with such people. This is because it causes both developed countries and developing countries to experience population growth.

The number of jobs that are accessible will be more than the number of workers in developed nations, which will lead to a decrease in average income as well as an increase in either unemployment or the number of highly educated people working in positions that need just a low degree of education. Meanwhile, less developed nations are falling more and further behind as a direct result of the loss of educated employees, which has a detrimental impact on their economy. Both results contribute to a less robust economy, which means that the brain drain has the potential to have an extremely negative impact on the economy of the whole globe. After all, it is to the disadvantage of the nations who are participating. In their study from 2011, Gibson and McKenzie noted that the problem of brain drain is not a recent development. It has been debated in some of the most renowned economics magazines, which is recognition, as it should be, that this is a field that has a large economic influence and is a source of considerable worry. The problem known as "brain drain" must be extensively investigated by economists since it has the capacity to influence not just the economics of a single nation, but also the economy of the whole globe.

2. The Problem Known as "Migration"

The issue that is referred to as "migration" refers to persons who have an elevated level of education but nonetheless choose to leave their own country in pursuit of better chances. These individuals are the sole resource that can lead to significant advancements in the economic structures of their own nation. Nations whose economies are still in the process of developing are dependent on a state of equilibrium in which other nations can benefit from their economies while more developed nations are prevented from getting all their resources, including educated workers. This state of equilibrium is essential for these nations. If this equilibrium is not preserved, their economy will

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not be rebuilt. Because brain drain may result in both good and bad outcomes, the question becomes: how should brain drain be understood, and how should the implications of brain drain be managed?

On a scale that accounts for social and economic factors, the drawbacks are more significant than the benefits. As a result, the destruction of intellectual capital needs to be seen as a horrific event.

- *It must be put a stop to, or at the very least, controlled.*

Undocumented immigrants who have completed post-secondary educations in their countries of residency should not be permitted to engage in illegal labor in the professions for which they have been trained. This is a method for managing the situation that has arisen. They often can labor for salaries that are below the legally authorized minimum wage or even for earnings that are unlawfully low, making it difficult or even impossible for persons with legal education to get equivalent positions. Additionally, industrialized nations are needed to implement more stringent procedures for the acquisition of licenses and work permits. In addition, developing nations have a greater responsibility to increase the level of competition and appeal of their labor markets to the greatest extent that is humanly practicable. If they are unable to provide their employees with the essential resources and equipment, they should seriously consider importing more current technology as well as facilities. Increase the amount of employment that need higher levels of education and make such possibilities more easily accessible if a developing nation wants to keep its population. This is one technique that may be used by a developing country that wants to retain its residents. In such case, workers will look for employment elsewhere. The government must adopt steps that are not just severe but also productive. However, they also need to watch their educated populations and interfere by adopting policies that will encourage educated individuals to remain in the region and contribute to the local economy. This is another responsibility that falls on the local government. It is the obligation of the government to safeguard these investments and to make certain that they are generating the outcomes that are sought.

Globalization may be seen of as the engine that powers the so-called "New Economy." It is expected that the negative effects of brain drain would lessen as economic development continues, particularly among people who have obtained elevated levels of education. Some nations struggle

to compete well on the international arena and provide compelling reasons for its educated citizens to remain in their country. As a result of globalization, it is now simpler than ever before for people to relocate to nations that provide greater earnings. They have the capacity to relocate to other locations that are more conducive to growth and provide greater chances. Companies and governments all around the globe are engaged in a "war of talent" to compete for competent people and keep the ones they have (Davis and Hart , 2010, p. 509).

3. Scope and General Course of Migration

When compared to the total quantity of migration that is taking place throughout the globe currently, the movement of skilled workers is of extraordinarily little consequence statistically. In 1993, it was estimated that between 70 and 85 million individuals may be classified as immigrants. However, even though migration is not a widespread phenomenon, it is still beneficial to provide an overview of its extent and general direction. This is because competency is always a qualitative factor that inhibits both growth and development. The movement that has received the greatest attention is the migration of professionally skilled employees from South and Central America to North America. These workers come from countries with elevated levels of educational attainment. Between the years 1960 and 1990, the United States and Canada each attracted about one million skilled immigrants from emerging nations. These people came to their countries through immigration programs. Most of these people were brought here from Asia and Latin America.

Surprisingly, the nations in the Caribbean and Central America that are physically placed the closest to one another are the ones who have been hit the worst by the hurricane. These nations are witnessing a considerable number of their business middle classes as well as university graduates leaving for countries in the North as a direct consequence of this trend. Within South America itself, there is a significant amount of immigration from neighboring countries to Venezuela, Mexico, Argentina, and Brazil. On the other hand, significant numbers of academics and workers with professional qualifications migrate from Argentina and Colombia to the United States, and now an increasing number migrate to Spain and Italy. This migration happens in both directions at the same time. In Asia, Japan and Australia have been successful in luring skilled immigrants from

the areas around them for an exceptionally long time. In more recent times, countries that are farther along in the industrialization process, such as Singapore, have also become destinations for immigrants with relevant skills.

4. Economic and Social Consequences

The key aspect that will determine the economic and social effects that will result from the immigration of immigrants is the degree to which the issue of individual immigrants or the whole economic community of the countries of origin or destination is addressed. Evaluations are conducted with competent individuals from poor nations. The second aspect that will be taken into consideration when determining how the evaluation will be conducted is whether the problem will be addressed in terms of industrialized nations or developing countries. At the level of the individual, it is arguable that immigration is the result of potential immigrants' professional career planning, which, if successful, provides them with monetary and frequently non-monetary benefits. If this is the case, then immigration is the result of professional career planning. It is possible to say, without equivocation, that immigration is the result of potential immigrants' professional career planning when the decision to migrate is solely dependent on the wishes of the immigrant. This is the case in situations in which the decision to migrate depends entirely on the wishes of the immigrant.

Graphic -1: Brain Drain from Developing Countries 1995 and 2000¹

North-South Relations and New Zealand have, for an exceptionally long time, worked together to create an atmosphere that encourages immigration from persons who have achieved an elevated level of success in their professional and academic lives. Even if the mobility of all kinds of factors, including intellectual migration, contributes to an increase in the wealth of the global society, the advantages of welfare are still unequally divided across two sets of countries that are associated with one another. While the percentage of wealth owned by industrialized nations continues to rise, the percentage of wealth held by countries in the Third World that are the places of origin of immigrants continues to fall. This may seem to be in accordance with the law of markets, which states that those who are more prepared in the economy will constantly improve their position, while those who are less equipped will always fall farther behind.

There is no question that making attempts to settle problems in developing nations by peaceful ways would make people feel less of a need to flee the country. This is a well-established fact. The World Development Report from 1995 provides evidence on the degree to which liberal reforms and a policy of adapting to market forces can remove the causes of intellectual migration. The

¹https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Brain-Drain-from-Developing-Countries-1995-2000_fig3_321184126

report notes that many countries, including Turkey, returned home after the liberalization of industrialization policy.

It is true that industrialized countries are not the only ones responsible for intellectual migration; however, they must do everything possible to increase the attractiveness of Third World countries for qualified citizens, including by promoting programs to reintegrate skilled workers into their home countries. This involves doing everything necessary to promote the appeal of Third World nations to competent residents. Because education may help to developing a country's ability to engage in an increasingly knowledge-based global economy and accelerate economic progress, the development community has intensified its attention on higher education during the last two decades. This is a recognition of the reality that education may aid expedite economic progress. The value that higher education adds to economies in the form of job creation, innovation, increased entrepreneurialism, and research, one of the primary activities in which higher education institutions are involved, has been the subject of a substantial amount of published research, which has shed light on the value that higher education adds to economies. It is essential to note, however, that funding higher education in less developed nations might lead to a "brain drain," which is a phrase for the long-term emigration of highly educated students and professionals from their native country.

5. Components and Procedures

If health systems are unable to replace the human capital that they have lost because of an increase in the number of medical physicians and other health professionals, then there is a good chance that these systems will collapse. According to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, developed nations have a responsibility to aid developing nations to help them meet the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of providing universal health care by the year 2030. (SDGs). It is crucial to provide financial assistance to these nations as a means of helping them; but it may be even more critical to reform laws on immigration and recruiting to alleviate shortages in the health workforce in developing countries.

Second, Alkire and Chen state that wealthy nations may need to modify their immigration and recruiting rules to make room for medical professionals who have received their education in another nation. This "medical exceptionalism" will entail providing these experts with a higher level of priority care. It is possible that the World Health Organization's Global Code of Practice on the International Recruitment of Healthcare Professionals is connected to this moral conundrum. The complexity of the patterns and impacts of healthcare migration, which affects the implementation of the Code, is nonetheless a key obstacle that must be overcome. Due to the limited number of empirical studies that have been undertaken on the topic, the empirical foundation for policy decisions regarding the recruitment of health professionals who have been educated in other countries is quite flimsy. The lack of data availability is a barrier to the conduct of more empirical research as well as the monitoring of the recruitment of health professionals who have been educated globally in other countries. Most nations that send migrants in the health sector do not typically provide figures to WHO on a regular basis. The overwhelming majority do not have access to a system that is effective for documenting data linked to migration.

In future research endeavors, data collecting, in the form of surveys, need to be a primary emphasis. The findings of the surveys provide researchers with the opportunity to investigate health care migration as well as individual-level factors that have an impact on health, which may make a substantial contribution to multilevel analyses.

Third, nations with high incomes need to lessen their dependency on countries with low and intermediate incomes for the employment of medical professionals.

5.1 Availability of Earning Opportunities

The ability of healthcare workers to find employment in the international market is dependent on several factors, some of which include but are not limited to economic downturns; changes in the immigration policy of destination countries; recognition of academic papers from certain sending countries; and the unpredictability that results from events such as the COVID-19 pandemic. These factors are important.

In 1960, the United Kingdom was the first nation to use the term "Brain Drain" to describe the phenomenon that occurred when talented employees started to migrate from emerging or undeveloped countries to industrialized nations. The term "global brain drain" was used to describe this exodus (first world countries). It is a word that is used to describe the phenomena of people who, despite having an elevated level of education and professional ability, leave their native country to seek permanent residency in another developed nation. The concept is also known as the "brain drain." This problem is also referred to as human capital flight in certain circles. With the rise of globalization came the beginning of an era marked by an intensified exchange of thoughts, points of view, and capabilities across nations. This was conducted via the use of competent workers.

5.2 Push and Pull Factors

The factors that contribute to an increased brain drain are often referred to by two different names: push factors and pull factors. The components that are connected to the country of origin are referred to as Push factors. Pull factors are factors that are associated with the country that will ultimately be visited. The primary facility does not supply an environment that is suitable for research and teaching in institutions that are taken into consideration as driving factors. There is a severe lack of employment opportunities for the thousands of graduates in engineering, scientists, and technicians who are currently on hold for a variety of assignments. unstable political relationships and a generally poor standard of living characterize this region. Access to medical facilities has become extremely difficult to obtain. Several factors, including improved economic prospects, contribute to the attractiveness.

1. *Better facilities for research.*
2. *Employment opportunities.*
3. *Stability in Politics*
4. *Enhanced prospects for a contemporary education system and career advancement.*

There are three distinct manifestations of the phenomenon known as "brain drain." The phrase "geographic Brain Drain" refers to the migration of highly educated professionals from one developing nation to another in pursuit of jobs with better wages. This migration occurs most often between countries in Africa and Southeast Asia. It is damaging to the development of the economic atmosphere of one's native nation and slows down economic growth. The departure of experienced and skilled workers from one organization and their later recruitment by another is referred to as "organizational brain drain." The fact that they avoid going inside institutions may be quite harmful to their health. The phenomena of employees with specialized knowledge and skills transferring from one industry to another in quest of greater salaries is referred to as the "industrial brain drain." This phrase was used to explain the phenomenon. Because of this, there is a dearth of experienced employees in the industry in which they first made their debut. The phenomenon that is being referred to by the phrase "brain drain" is one that is happening more often in the modern society. Countries in varying phases of development and backwardness, such as India, African and Arab countries, are among those suffering from a loss of talent and qualified professionals. Other countries in the developing world also face this problem. To better manage this situation and strive toward creating an atmosphere that is more pleasant and inviting, governments and commercial enterprises alike need to institute certain stringent rules. It should expand the number of job chances, enhance pay, improve working conditions, offer better infrastructure in educational institutions, generate more employment prospects, and invest in the development of rural areas. It is imperative that workplaces be made free of discrimination and prejudice, and this can only be conducted by the passage of legislation and the rigorous upholding of existing standards. By supplying financial incentives, young people should be dissuaded from leaving their home nations in search of economic opportunities elsewhere. There is a possibility that addressing the brain drain issue may be conducted by the implementation of these action measures.

6. Motivation

The phenomenon known as the "brain drain," which refers to the movement of highly educated people from poor countries to rich countries, has its primary focus on this migration of highly

educated people. This phenomenon occurs in the context of an international transfer of human capital resources. The term is often used in a more restricted sense, and more specifically refers to the migration of engineers, doctors, scientists, and other highly skilled professionals with university education, with the migration taking place primarily between developed countries. Comparative data show that there were 20 million immigrants with high levels of education living in OECD member countries in the year 2000. This number is a rise of 70 percent in just ten years. Workers from other countries who have completed post-secondary education are an example of highly skilled immigrants.

6.1 Discussing the Advantages and Disadvantages

Important recent shifts in the distribution of highly skilled employees According to the Global Migration Database of the United Nations, the number of persons who traveled across international boundaries increased from 75 million in 1960 to 214 million in 2010. This is a significant increase. This nearly exactly corresponds with the rise in the population of the globe; hence, this indicates that the worldwide migration rate has increased rather moderately, going from 2.5% to 3.1% of the total population. According to the findings of the global bilateral migration database that was released in 2011, movement between poor nations continues to account for most of the world's migrant stock. The movement of people from less developed nations to more developed countries, which more than doubled from 10 million to 55 million between 1960 and 2000, was the primary factor behind the rise in the overall number of immigrants. This growth occurred at a quicker rate than that of commerce during this time. Since 1960, there has been a significant increase in the proportion of people migrating from low-income countries to high-income countries, and this has been the primary driver of the overall increase in the number of international immigrants. Since 1960, there has been a significant increase in the proportion of people migrating from low-income countries to high-income countries. The proportion of persons with elevated levels of education and professional experience who leave their nation is usually always greater than the percentage of

those with lower levels of education and professional experience who leave their country. The skills bias that may be shown in migration rates is more pronounced in nations with lower incomes.

Negative consequences Given the many technological and sociological externalities, the societal return on investment in human capital is extremely likely to outweigh private advantages. This is because of the many technical and sociological externalities (see Terms used in migration studies). This debate on the effects of externalities has been an important part of study on the topic ever since the 1970s. The conclusion that brains drain generates large losses for those who are left behind and raises global inequality is presented in a major contribution to this area of research

6.2 Additional Positive Feedback Loops

In general, immigrants who have completed higher levels of education are those who send more money back to their home countries. It is hard to analyze the effect of highly skilled remittances on investment, poverty, or inequality in the home nation since there are no surveys that match sending and receiving households. It is expected that the economic consequences of remittances will vary significantly depending on the home nation.

6.3 Circular Migration

Return migration, also known as circular movement or repeated return migration, is a strategy to guarantee that the host country and home nation enjoy the benefits of highly skilled labor mobility. There is reason to be positive about return migration to do this. The added knowledge and financial capital that returnees buy while abroad supplies significant benefits, particularly for the adoption of modern technologies, encouraging entrepreneurship, and increasing overall productivity. In developing countries, the possibility of temporary migration increases educational returns and has the same effects on human capital formation as permanent, uncertain migration. In addition, the

possibility of temporary migration has the same effects on human capital formation as permanent, uncertain migration. This explains why return intentions are similar across skill categories since the return possibilities are highly affected by the present economic and political circumstances in the homeland. It is generally accepted, despite the fact that return migration is arguably the aspect of international migration that has the least amount of documentation, that historical examples of mass return migration of highly skilled workers were more of a result than a cause for development and sound policy. Reform in their home countries, diaspora externalities, and immigrants with specialized talents all have the potential to lower the costs of conducting business across nations. This, in turn, may encourage international commerce, foreign direct investment, and the exchange of technical ability. Additionally, the diaspora can have an external effect on the quality of institutions and the development of democracy in the country of origin. To begin, there is a connection between brain drain and growth. Furthermore, when the migration rate is large, the effect of brain drain is unquestionably detrimental. Second, the current state of the global economy, which is in a recession, is the primary motivating factor for the movement of recent college graduates to other nations. Interactions between these two elements may result in both negative and positive feedback loops, which are related with individuals' migration decisions and choices. As soon as a significant brain drain gets underway, it may have a negative impact on the economy, which can then lead to further waves of movement by highly trained individuals. It's possible that the consequences of the first brain drain are what's causing these waves (Iran after the 1978-1979 revolution, the Irish crisis in the early 1980s, former USSR republics after 1991).

6.4 Concerns About Both the Economy and Culture

It is essential to have a clear understanding that the idea of "brain drain" has always been a contentious one. This is particularly true considering the confusion that has surrounded current arguments about how to solve the challenges brought about by the departure of bright persons. This dissatisfaction is a direct result of the movement of highly educated people from less developed countries to more developed countries. Many nationalist leaders, who thought that their efforts to construct a country were being impeded by the immigration of their most gifted young, saw it as a

neocolonial phenomenon. They believed that it was hindering their ability to build a country. It was assumed that a decrease in the quantity of productive skills bought by the people was one of the primary reasons for the economic underdevelopment that occurred. It shouldn't come as much of a surprise that nationalist and internationalist viewpoints on the influence of brain drain on economic growth arrive at starkly opposed conclusions about the matter. Brain drain is a natural process that maximizes welfare, income, and development, according to internationalists. On the other hand, according to nationalists, brain drain is a process that results in the loss of national income, welfare, and development while simultaneously reinforcing global patterns of inequality.

7. Explanatory Variables

It is possible that the choices of immigrants about their destination may be explained by a broad range of economic and non-economic factors. The migration rate is dependent on a variety of variables that run as push factors at the origin, pull forces at the destination, cultural and geographical distances, and immigration restrictions

The World Development Indicators give statistics on several population-related topics (World Bank, 2005). In several different regressions, it is possible to examine the interaction variables between small states, fractionation, and GDP per capita to discover the extent to which small states' immigration rates are susceptible to several different drivers. In this case, according to the observation that people living in small states have a higher population density than people living in other countries. This can be demonstrated by looking at the RF values that are positive and the interaction variables that are also positive. In other words, power migration from small states is more sensitive to fluctuations in per capita GDP than migration from large states, as indicated by the negative and values of the interaction coefficients. This is indicated by interaction negatives having a value (GDP per capita x small). This result is an estimate of different migrating cells as well as highly resistant to different waits. Migration estimates in small states are environmental with lower estimates than other nations, confirming the estimate that immigration estimates in small states may be lower than in other nations. However, the difference in influence

between smaller states and bigger states is minimal, ranging from around one percent to two percent. This is because larger states have a greater population.

8. Understanding the Brain Drain on Three Fronts

There are several considerations that go into the decision to leave one's homeland or territory, the most prevalent of which are as follows:

1. Economic possibilities, such as newly generated and better jobs, greater living standards, access to housing and medical care, and so forth.
2. Social prospects, such as enhanced access to education and cultural opportunities.
3. Conflicts and a politically unstable environment
4. The act of harassing another individual based on their religion, gender, or sexual orientation
5. While geographical factors are certainly to blame, there are also certain occurrences that may be traced back to the circumstances that were there at the time.

For instance, when human labor is replaced by automation and technology, competent people may choose to quit their company and the sector altogether. The issue that is often referred to as "brain drain" is also sometimes referred to as "human capital flight."

Loss of intellectual capital may have major implications. Not only are the consequences felt in the area that experiences a brain drain, but they are also felt in the region that experiences brain acquisition. The depletion of human capital in the regions that are affected by brain drain is the direct consequence of this phenomenon. When skilled workers go to other countries in search of better opportunities, they leave behind a significant hole that is not always simple to replace. Take, for instance, the movement of healthcare professionals from less developed regions of the globe to more developed areas of the world in the hope of finding better career prospects. It is possible that they will not be replaced by an adequate number of (capable) persons when they leave, which will have an impact on the quality of health care offered to those who are left behind. The loss of

revenue is another impact that may be seen in areas that are subjected to brain drain. Most of the financing for social programs and infrastructure projects that undertake comes from revenue collected via income taxes. When vast numbers of people move away from an area, the quantity of tax income that is collected drops, which slows down the overall growth and development of the economy. A bigger population in a locality makes demands on the existing resources, which may result increasing expenditures and taxes if they are not adequately met.

There is no easy answer to the problem of brain drain; however, there are several things that leaders in both industry and government can do to lessen or compensate for its effects. These include:

- 1. Boosting the level of financial investments made in certain areas of the economy*
- 2. Supplying competitive wages*
- 3. Developing a strategy for constitutional and socioeconomic reform that will move the process forward*
- 4. Improving the quality of services and facilities that are currently offered, such as housing and medical care*
- 5. Supplying housing alternatives that are easily available*

Migration is a consequence of the imbalance that exists between the rise of the population and the development of the economy. This results in a good supply of competent individuals for affluent nations, but in LDCs and emerging countries there is underemployment and a lack of educated population, which results in a shortage of trained labor.

There are seeing an alarmingly significant increase in the number of students from other nations who are leaving their homes to seek higher education in other countries. 25 percent of the respondents in the survey conducted by Tansel and Güngör concluded that they chose to study abroad because of the prestige of studying abroad and the convenience of studying there. The scarcity of technologically modern laboratories, equipment and instruments in Turkey was a major contributor to the brain drain in that country. Immigrants from Turkey did not want to return to their home countries due to the political unpredictability, the unstable state of the economy and the lack of prospects for professional advancement. Iravani was the person who conducted the research in Iran using census data collected from the United Nations Education and Research Institute. The

key factors to the brain drain were the T-psychosocial issue, unstable economic situations, and insecure political contexts. There is a significant and worrisome issue of educated people being unable to find work in several nations throughout the world, including China, India, Pakistan, Iran, Nigeria, South Korea, the Philippines, and Colombia. This is a problem that needs to be fixed as soon as possible. (“Fix Printer Error 0X8000Fff Catastrophic Failure On Windows 11 10”) Iravani concluded that the primary factors contributing to brain drain are a lack of job creation, jobs that are unsuitable for job qualifications, overproduction, and a lack of experience necessary to compete for jobs that require an elevated level of academic excellence, productivity, and training. It has been shown that the issue of brain drain may be mitigated by providing individuals with employment that match their knowledge for them to demonstrate that they are competent in such occupations. Simon Commander concluded that the greatest detrimental factor to the expansion of the nation was the "brain drain," which was brought on by the emigration of talented people. This finding was based on his examination of both the theoretical and empirical research in the field. (Gouda et al.) Governments need to come up with new policies to guarantee that educated employees have access to employment possibilities in their respective sectors, and they need to do this as soon as possible. The revival of nationalism is one of the major factors that is contributing to the unfavorable outlook that emerging countries have towards immigration. On the other hand, growing nationalism is associated with the development of more restrictive immigration policies, which are currently in place in industrialized countries that are trying to reestablish barriers. A new strain of xenophobia surfaced in the United States in the wake of the terrorist events that took place in New York City on September 11, 2001. It is expected that this xenophobia will continue to influence migration, and as a result, there will be a reduction in the number of highly educated people who migrate. (Hart 2006). There is a possibility that the "Brain Drain" issue will be solved on its own if the immigration regulations that are already in place continue to grow more rigorous. Altering the language that is used to discuss the matter is one more choice that has been recommended as a possible solution to the problem. In other words, we need to drop making use of the term "Brain Drain" since even the mere uttering of this phrase instantly elicits an adverse response from individuals. Because of this, Hart (2006) suggests that the term "High Skilled

Migration" be used since it better truly captures the nature of the phenomena that is taking place and offers a more distinct image of the issue that is now being faced.

9. Situation and Evaluation for Turkey

Brain drain is important as it is a concept that expresses the movement of highly qualified individuals from their own countries to other countries. These individuals usually have a diploma from an accredited university or the equivalent of a degree from an accredited university in any field. The movement of educated people from underdeveloped countries to more developed countries from the 1950s aroused the curiosity of economists and educators who began to focus more on this issue after the 1950s (Adams, 1971; Iredale, 2001). (Adams, 1971; Iredale, 2001). After these years, people have tried to explain the loss of brain power by tying it to various economic, political and social causes. Although brain drain from developing countries to industrialized countries occurs often, there are other forms of brain drain (Ghosh, 1982). There is no such thing as a brain drain if there is a movement of competent people from country to country (Thomas, 1973). What does not qualify as a "brain drain" is the scenario where competent people leave an organization because they are not used to their full potential. This kind of migration is a type of brain overflow that is not dangerous for the individual (Thomas, 1973). The term "hidden brain drain" refers to another type of brain drain (Adams, 1971). A disguised brain drain can occur when a country's skilled workforce is exported to work in foreign companies. This can happen in any country. Apart from that, research has shown that people who study in other countries tend to be less productive after returning to their home country. It is possible to interpret it as a disguised brain drain. There are various views on the brain drain. One school of thought holds that scientific research has a global dimension. Wherever a person is born, the definition of scientist includes the idea that he is at the service of both science and humanity. In this environment, it is the most natural privilege of a scientist to evaluate his talent in the best working conditions and, as a result, to serve humanity. Because the advantages provided by qualified people are not limited to a single setting; rather, they are scattered all over the world wherever these individuals travel (Blough, 1970; Adams, 1971; Grabel, 1982).

From a unique perspective, the movement of skilled people from developing countries to more developed countries are beneficial for the latter. As a result, the growth of poor nations is hampered. Therefore, trained personnel who play a key role in development should be kept in the country of origin (Adams, 1971). (Adams, 1971). In later years, he emigrated from Germany under the reign of the Nazis. After the 18th century, countries in Central Asia and the Balkans were considered possible entry points for immigrants moving to Turkey. It is believed that between 1771 and 1989, approximately 10 million people came to Anatolia in search of a better life.

Üçcan (1993), 7.8 million entered the country before the proclamation of the Republic, while only 2.2 million entered the country during the Republican period. On the other hand, there were also those who went to other countries from Turkey from time to time. In the years leading up to the First World War, thousands of people of many nationalities who were part of Ottoman society moved, mostly to the United States. Most of the people moved during these times due to political and war related factors. Changes in economic, transport and communication systems over the past few decades are largely responsible for most of today's migrations. During the 1980s, countries in the Middle East began to seek skilled labor from Turkey. It is estimated that around 10% of the skilled workforce in Turkey works elsewhere in the world (Erkal, 1992).

According to statistics compiled by the United Nations between 1962 and 1967, an average of 375 Turkish scientists a year left their homeland to pursue careers elsewhere. 51.1% of the immigrants come from the field of medicine, 40% from the field of engineering, 5.5% from the natural sciences and 3% from the social sciences (Erkal, 1992). According to the Second Five-Year Plan, 8.2% of specialist physicians, 8.2% of general practitioners, 5.3% of mechanical engineers and 21.4% of architects left their countries in search of work until 1970. Research by Turhan Ozkan revealed that 81.3% of Turks currently employed in the United States received their education from an institution found outside of Turkey. Of these, 46.7% received their most recent degree from a school found in the United States. According to these facts, the problem of brain drain is a problem noticed by individuals studying abroad in Turkey as well as in many other countries.

9.1 Economic Insufficiencies

One of the most significant factors that contributes to the phenomenon that is referred to as "brain drain" is the gap that exists between the standard of living in the country of origin and the standard of living in the country to which people migrate. On the one hand, factors such as unemployment, low earnings, and a lack of job prospects within the country are some of the driving forces behind migration. On the other hand, factors such as employment level and income chances in the target country are attractive factors. Because of this, nations that are successful in reversing the trend of brain drain by attracting skilled emigrants tend to pay higher wages to those immigrants. This is one of the factors that contributes to that country's ability to keep hold of its highly skilled personnel.

9.2 Academic Disability

Because of globalization, people's expectations have shifted, and this shift in people's wants has caused a transformation in education; the aim of teaching people to teach people to teach people to teach people to teach people to instruct people has moved to the forefront. People from nations that were unable to provide this opportunity for their citizens began migrating to other countries to satisfy their requirements. Specifically, the instability of the education system, the presence of crossovers in the school system, unfavorable working conditions, a lack of promotion opportunities, and a lack of working culture are among the factors that are contributing to this problem (Yilmaz, 2019: 227).

9.3 Technological Inadequacies

Technology resources in target countries include, but are not limited to, the ability to study a foreign language, conduct research in a laboratory, conduct web-based searches more quickly, find articles more easily, use libraries and advanced computers, and learn a foreign language. During our investigation, we are going to require these various technical tools as essential components. (Yilmaz, 2019: 227) The availability of financial aid in the form of grants or scholarships provided by the government or other organizations is another factor that encourages individuals to remain in

a country and continue their education there. This type of assistance can be obtained by the individual.

9.4 Skilled Personnel Migration from Turkey with Statistics

It is possible to investigate the data concerning the emigration of talented people from Turkey to other nations. The Dutch Immigration and Citizenship Authority (IND) received a total of 1020 applications from academics and other highly educated individuals during the first 11 months of 2018. These individuals wished to move to the Netherlands. (BBC, 2019). It has been seen that academics and other highly educated people who want to leave the country complain about a "lack of freedom in the country." [Citation needed] This institution has supplied special statistics for the previous years, and these statistics show that the number of people who emigrated from Turkey to the Netherlands to further their education increased from 540 in 2016 to 780 in 2017. Because of this, it is reasonable to assert that the brain drain is becoming more severe with each passing year. More than 50,000 students from Turkey leave the country every year to pursue higher education in other countries, as indicated by statistics provided by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). According to the statistics compiled by TUIK, the number of people leaving Turkey totaled 330 289 in just the year 2019. In 2015, the Council at Risk Academics in the United Kingdom received applications from 4-5 international scientists and academics each week; in 2016, the number of applications received per week increased to 15-20. Stephen Wordsworth, director of the Council at Risk Academics, noted this increase.

9.5 Increase in demand from Turkey (World University)

Because each migration is unique in comparison to the others, migrations are often separated into two primary categories: voluntary and forcible. In addition, immigrants may be broken down into several other categories, including asylum seekers, refugees, voluntary migrants, and immigrants. The Push-Pull Theory, Petersen's Five Types of Migration, and the Intersecting Opportunities Theory were all used in this investigation to comprehend and make sense of the reasons why many

different migration patterns occur. Over the course of the last several years, this issue has grown more widespread, particularly in Turkey. Inadequacies in employment, insufficient education, lack of motivation to work, library and technological inadequacies are seen to be the causes of brain drain in Turkey. Although the brain drain in Turkey originates from a wide spectrum of sources, these factors have been seen to be the causes of brain drain in Turkey. The phenomenon that is known as a "brain drain" is considerably exacerbated by the fact that highly educated and brilliant Turks often leave their home country in order to explore opportunities elsewhere. Scientists with extraordinary talents who are unable to get their high-level abilities evaluated and who cannot find an environment in which to conduct their job often go overseas. People who live in developed nations tend to be more receptive to novel ideas and strategies for furthering the progress of their country because they have more opportunity to do so. Because of this, industrialized nations can close the gap in terms of total growth with less developed ones. There are parallels to be drawn between the experiences of Turkey and those of other emerging nations about the loss of highly trained personnel because of the brain drain. These are the outcomes of the significant differences, both economically and technically, that exist between emerging nations and industrialized ones. It is more probable that the values of a nation will be exported if there is a system in place that requires students to study a foreign language as a required subject in schools (Kurtulmuş, 1992, pages 205-215). This is particularly true in nations that are still considered to be developing. It is likely that members of skilled labor forces who go abroad for training or experience will have increased brain power when they return to their previous jobs. The current state of education quality in Turkey, the limited resources distributed to science and scientific research, the inadequacy of the importance given to new research and values, and the factors that make Turkey dependent on other countries for the development of technological capabilities are all interconnected.

Rather than being a set of institutions that ease the adaptation of individuals who realize their personal development and follow technological innovations to societal changes, the education system should have a content that aims to train individuals as active elements in the realization of these changes and innovations. If industrialized countries maintain more desirable standards for employment and opportunities, as well as the expectation that those who move there will have a better future, the brain drain will unavoidably continue. In this light, the socio-economic

repercussions of the ongoing economic crises present an extremely critical and urgent situation for Turkey as well as for every other country going through a crisis that is analogous to the one Turkey is going through. To get rid of this unfavorable circumstance, the first thing that needs to be done is to stabilize our nation economically and politically. It is possible for societies to expand if science, technology, and brain power that has been properly educated are given the importance that is due to them. It is of the utmost significance for Turkey to devise and put into action strategies that can put an end to the brain drain.

9.6 Studies on Brain Drain in Turkey

Tuzcu University conducted a study in 2014 under the heading "Brain Drain from Turkey to Spain." An online interview form has been sent to recent university graduates living in Spain who obtained their degrees from Turkish educational institutions. There were responses supported 180 of these forms. Researcher Tuzcu looked over and responded to the forms that were filled out. The following is a sampling of the findings that were discovered:

- *The absence of an established industrial system in Turkey is the primary reason university graduates choose to search for work in Spain rather than remaining in their native country. This is the case in contrast to the situation in Spain, where there is such a system.*

College graduates who have recently entered the workforce are less inclined to trust organizations that have a history of opening and shutting their doors often. Many students who graduate from institutions in Turkey have an interest in finding employment in multinational corporations located in other countries, such as Skoda (Wolkswagen) in Spain. The second reason is that the bulk of Turkey's manufacturing sector is made up of family businesses, and it is exceedingly difficult to alter the values and traditions that are deeply ingrained in Turkish families. It is not unheard of for family firms to promote members of the family to managerial positions despite those family members lacking in either ability or abilities. These managers do not set up a sense of vision in their workers, and therefore, they deplete their employees' drive and hinder their employees from coming to their senses. In 2008, the findings of Gokbayrak's research entitled "International

Debates on Migration and Development: A Study on Brain Drain" were published in a book by the same name. The study was based on an analysis of the prior research that had been conducted on the topic. This study, which examines the effects of migration and development within the scope of brain drain, which has come to the forefront in international migration in recent years, has revealed that these effects cannot be accepted as general truths. According to what he said, these outcomes are not going to occur unless the environment is shaped in a way that is consistent with the principles of responsible public policy. He put a significant amount of stress on awareness raising as well as the need of public policies to ensure a positive externality in the development that was the outcome of the brain drain. Bakırtaş and Kandemir published their findings from their study named "Developing Countries and Brain Drain: The Case of Turkey" in the year 2010. According to the findings of this research, although there is an intense pressure on unemployment rates for higher education graduates in Turkey, the ease with which educated individuals in industrialized countries can find work is the primary factor that contributes to brain drain. This is the case even though Turkey's unemployment rates for college graduates are extremely high. Inadequate resources distributed to research and development and, as a result, inadequate working conditions for scientists in the country are another factor that contributes to the brain drain. This is one of the factors that is one of the contributing factors to the brain drain. It was hypothesized that those who had completed a higher degree of education could prefer countries that offered them superior standards of life.

Cansız is the one who conducted the research and had it published in 2009 under the title "The Effects of Brain Drain on Turkish Higher Education in Recent Years." This study aimed to analyze the variables that contribute to the brain drain in Turkey as well as their consequences on the higher education system in that country. It has been said that there is a lack of trustworthy statistics about the brain drain in Turkey, and that the country's existing knowledge does not extend farther than the ability of certain institutions. The United States of America, Canada, Australia, England, France, and Germany are just few of the developed nations that receive help from Turkey's skilled labor exports. These nations are among the most significant contributors to the loss of intellectual talent that is experienced by industrialized nations. Even though it is common knowledge that our nation suffers from a lack of qualified personnel and that this lack will continue to worsen over the

next few years, it is evident that there are still some factors that will encourage individuals to choose other options. Our country is in jeopardy of losing its chance to keep up with contemporary developments because academics who are sent overseas do not return due to employment concerns or inadequate living conditions in their host countries.

Chart – 8: For this indicator, we provide data for Turkey from 2007 to 2022. The average value for Turkey in this period is 4.33 index points, a minimum of 3.6 index points in 2016 and a maximum of 5 index points in 2007. The latest value is 3.9 index points from 2022. For comparison, the world average for 177 countries in 2022 is 5.21 index points.²

At the same time as there has been a rise in the need for highly trained labor force, which is seen to be missing in development initiatives, a common environment for brain drain has been developed.

One of the nations that is suffering from a loss of intellectual talent is Turkey. The accumulation of these impacts, together with the benefit of experience, has shown that for them to be realized, certain preconditions need to be satisfied within the context of responsible public policy. When conducting an examination of these policies, it is very necessary to take into consideration the immigration limitations that are imposed by industrialized nations. Therefore, in this scenario, the nature of international migration will alter depending on the public policies that will enable this externality to exist and increase awareness of this issue. In other words, the character of movement

²https://www.theglobaleconomy.com/Turkey/human_flight_brain_drain_index/

across international borders will change. Migration is a significant phenomenon that takes place in all eras, beginning in the past and continuing into the current day.

10. Conclusion

Especially developing countries; to make up for the losses they've suffered at the hands of developed countries, they've instituted programs to stem the flow of talent in the opposite direction. Countries like India, China, South Korea, Thailand, and Taiwan, which are known to suffer from brain drain, have adopted various measures to reduce brain drain, such as laws and programs aimed at reversing the trend. These countries include India, China, South Korea, Thailand, and Taiwan. One type of brain drain is when highly skilled people move from developed countries to developing countries that are suffering from the loss of brain drain. An example of this would be the process of attracting highly skilled people from developed countries. The term "brain drain" may also be used to refer to the practice of luring people from more prosperous nations. In this study, the policies of developing countries that contribute to brain drain, also known as "brain drain," were analyzed. These measures are in direct opposition to those that have been developed by industrialized nations all around the globe to combat the brain drain phenomenon. The issue of brain drain in the opposite direction is one that is being discussed in Turkey, as it is in a great many other nations around the world. In this context, it is common knowledge that the Turkish organizations TÜBTAK, ASELSAN, and HAVELSAN collaborated with a substantial number of other organizations to develop initiatives and policies. However, the factors that ease and complicate the adaptation to working life and daily life abroad are the same factors that facilitate and complicate the adaptation process. The education that they receive abroad is effective in the brain drain of highly qualified individuals in line with their professional gains. It has been determined that job postings and scholarships are effective in their employment. It has also been determined that the employment opportunities offered to them as a reason for working in the institutions they work in are effective. The regulation of working relations and the increase in scientific support are on the agenda. On the other hand, it shines brightest in the suggestions it puts out for the actualization and expansion of brain drain. It has also been determined that the

employment opportunities that are being offered to them as a reason are effective, which is relevant when discussing the process of beginning a job in Turkey after the reverse brain drain.

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